

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE IMAGE OF ROMANIAN STATE NATIONALISM AT THE BEGINNING OF THE 20TH CENTURY

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Abstract

In the present article I aim to draw a picture of the idea of nation and nation-state starting from the very beginning of the conceptualization of the term and then, after observing the characteristics of the Romanian version of the concept and its development I make a comparison with Hungarian nationalism in the period under review.

Keywords: Romania, Hungary, nationalism, nation state, 19th century, 20th century, Transylvania

Nationalism, nation state and state nationalism

It is advisable to broaden the context and move it back in time to the birth of the 'modern nation', if only because we can see that the concept of nation is one of the political-philosophical and historical concepts whose interpretation is still (or increasingly) subject to imprecision and confusion.

As regards the first moments of the emergence of the 'nation', the Hungarian historian, Jenő Szűcs says that *'After the beginnings of humanism, the nation was made the immanent framework of history by the European Enlightenment of the 18th century, after the historical view had finally broken with the view of the history of humanity as the fulfilment of a divine World Plan.* Therefore the French Revolution has a key role to play – as it is not only the theoretical but also the practical source of the 'nation'.

Most literature agrees that there were two main paths of development in Europe towards modern nationhood; the Western European civic model led to the emergence of the nation-state (*Staatsnation*), while the German-based Central- and Eastern European model led to the emergence of the concept of *Kulturnation*. As the concept of nation first appeared in France in the second third of the 18th century – where the French language-border largely coincided with the political border of the state – the concept was first defined in terms of the relationship between the territory of the state, a common language and a common legal order. In other words, it is the growing state that creates the nation – incorporating the provincial nationalities (*les nationalités provinciales*) and then the political nation.

The potential ethnic, cultural and/or linguistic distinctiveness is marginal in the French model with practically no meaningful role – in contrast to the German-type concept of *Kulturnation*. Here, east of the Rhine, the 'nation-shaping' role of the state was absent. The political, economic and social development of the central and eastern regions of Europe, which differed from that of the west, presented a very different picture at the time when the national idea materialised. The imperial, multilingual and multi-religious frameworks covering vast territories, such as the Habsburg Monarchy or the Russian and Ottoman Empires, did not allow any of the

ethnic communities in the region to become a nation in the French way.

In contrast to the French model, the Herderian concept of *Kulturnation* – also known as the Oriental ethnic model – is based on the determination and fixation of a common language, culture and common ancestry. This concept created a utopia for nations in Eastern Europe that sought to transform cultural borders into political boundaries. As the German historian, Utz Jeggle put it, *'The borders of nation-states are a vision of one's own nationhood projected onto the surface of the earth, but offered only as a closed, not as an open, entity.'* Here, the problem with the other model becomes apparent, since in this case we are confronted with a kind of 'narrowing' conception of the nation, in which it is more difficult for a citizen with an ethnic identity to fit, since it is not the existence of the state that determines nationality. However, this dual or dichotomous conception is rejected by several authors – such as Rogers Brubaker or Alain Dieckhoff – pointing out that all modern nations bear the characteristics of both types at the same time; the emphasis is really on proportions.

But the nation-state had to be built, and nation-building was a consciously guided process by the elites, which in practice took root in society through the use of media, national curriculum and symbols. In a multi-ethnic state, this also created a bipolar problematic between the 'mainstream' and the minorities. The main idea of state, or 'nationalising' nationalism is that the 'main nation' is the legitimate owner of the state, which exists for the sake of the nation. The East-West difference here is that while in the West the idea of the nation was embedded in the framework of a multi-decade statehood, in the East the nation was assigned to the state without organic development.

Minority nationalism, on the other hand, is in practice the ethnopolitical strategy and reaction from national minorities against the nation-building of state nationalism, which is also one of the primary targets of its repression. However, this is partly a natural process, one of the most visible effects of which can be assimilation. In terms of its concrete instruments, the main element is state national policy, which takes the form of

nationalisation of national symbols, language use, public education and the media.

Thus, we can see that these two forms of nationalism in multi-ethnic states like Romania have been in constant struggle with each other from the very beginning – as opposing versions of nation-building in one state.

The birth and development of Romanian nationalism

Transylvania, however, is the birthplace of Romanian nationalism, as this region – for historical, cultural and geographical reasons – has always been much closer to the Western part of the continent than the two Danube principalities of Wallachia and Moldavia. The Transylvanian School played a pioneering role in the Romanian national awakening, which first unfolded in the recognition of Latin roots – and thus of the link with the West – by Greek Catholic students who went to Rome to study. In the imperial context, the Transylvanian Romanian (clerical) intellectuals who knew German were inevitably drawn closer to the idea of *Kultur-nation* by reading Herder's writings. Romanian historian, Sorin Mitu points out another aspect, namely that the Transylvanian Romanians 'learned' to be nationalist as a result of the 'competition' that was given in the region – where competition with other peoples was born out of a nationalist perception of threat.

In Moldavia and the Wallachian Lowlands, on the other hand, the increasingly close French connections of the boyar elites in the early 19th century really brought about the development of the idea of nationalism. The cultural divide that separated the principalities from Transylvania started to narrow step-by-step through Lamartine, Michelet, Mazzini or Mickiewicz until, by 1848, the foundations of a Romanian national cultural and political project had been laid. The following decades brought the reality closer and closer to the original idea – in 1859 the Small Unification took place, in 1866 the form of government changed to a constitutional monarchy, and certain cultural segments such as the Academy, literature, theatre, fine arts were established and flourished (in terms of cultural value) in the spirit of nationalist ideas.

This new political construction was intended to unite the community that the elite of the time in Bucharest called the Romanian nation – workers and peasants, Transylvanian Moți and Muslims from the seaside region of Dobrogea, or conservatives and people with socialist sentiments.

The Romanian version

The Romanian nationalism is a rather controversial variant, the central problem of which is that while from the birth (/creation) of the national ideology the Herderian cultural model of the nation prevailed as the basis for the image of the nation, the French model and the French state structure were used as the basis for the creation of the state framework. As the Romanian historian, Lucian Boia writes, '*the federal or autonomist formula was ruled out as early as the creation of Romania in 1859, even though it would have been the most obvious one.*' If only because the two old historical regions did not follow the same path of development, despite their common language. But what else could have

been an example but the most centralised state in Europe at a time when neither German nor Italian unity had yet been achieved? The contradiction became even deeper and more visible after the territorial expansion after the First World War.

The main ideological pillars of Romanian nationalism were the legitimacy of ancestry and the 'primordial occupation' as the source of historical law – thus the Daco-Roman ethnogenesis theory became a major element of national consciousness, and only later was the assertion of the geographical, geopolitical unity of the three principalities linked to it. Jenő Szűcs, in characterising the role of the Daco-Romans as a source of law, draws medieval analogies. What the French or the British of the 12th and 13th centuries saw in the squatters who had escaped from Troy; what the Norman of the 12th century saw in the Greek Danaans or the Hungarians in Attila and the Huns, the 20th century Romanian national consciousness saw in Burebista, Decebal and the Daco-Roman theory.

Romanian nationalism, however, has one feature which, although not entirely specific, is much more important than that of its neighbours, namely that it has always sought and found the essence of 'Romanian-ness' in the peasantry. The importance of the lowest stratum – the stratum that most characterises the nation – was also stressed by Herder, and was similarly present in the nationalisms of the neighbouring peoples, but given that even in 1930 more than 80% of the Romanian population lived in the countryside, the importance of the peasant way of life for the self-perception of the nation was more given than in most of the cases. The rural focus was indispensable if only because at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, practically only the countryside was 'Romanian', the more urbanised areas being ethnically quite diverse. One of the most illustrative examples is the case of the Moldavian historical capital Iași, where for a long period of time Jews built up the absolute majority in local society, but speaking about Transylvania, the proportion of Romanians within major settlements as Cluj, Oradea or Brașov has remained under 50% behind the Hungarians and Germans even until the Second World War.

The consequence of this ethnic embeddedness by the 1920s was that Romanians became in the public perception primarily 'Romanians' – or 'Romanian peasants' – and only secondarily 'Romanian citizens' or '(state) citizens'. The category of 'citizen' included Hungarians, Germans, Slavs with Romanian identity cards, but since here the 'selection' was based on the Herderian model, they did not become Romanians, like, say, the Bretons in France.

The 'socialist-national' model of the Ceaușescu era, which was to be applied a few decades later, did not include the Hungarians in the Romanian nation. The closest term that could come to this was 'brother nation', but the most common reference was 'the allied camp of working people of other nationalities who joined the Romanian people'.

The relation to historical Hungarian nationalism

Historical Hungarian nationalism is a special variant of Szűcs' definition, similar to the Czech and Polish examples. The subtype has as its starting point as the

medieval state, later classified as a national state, and the order which preserved its traditions in the face of the central power. Thus, by the early 19th century, a dual Hungarian nationalism had developed in Hungary: the *Kulturnation* national consciousness built on the Hungarian language and culture in opposition to the Habsburg government, while the *Staatsnation* national consciousness marked the borders of the nation in opposition to the nationalities. This is a fundamental difference from the Romanian form, where – with the exception of the Jews – there was no large-scale minority presence before 1918, and thus no possibility of developing a *Staatsnation* line.

However, it was not until a good fifty years later that Hungarian nationalism had the statehood framework of Romanian nationalism. After the unification of the principalities in 1859 – although de jure independence did not come until 1877 – as a de facto independent state it was able to create a relatively independent nationalism and to build it within concrete borders. However, a similar motive is to be found in both cases in the lack of participation of the bourgeoisie in the process, since in both cases it was the ruling elite that led the transition.

In contrast, under dualism (period of the Austro-Hungarian Empire from 1867 to 1918), we can speak of a kind of 'public nationalism', as exemplified by the English model, with the big difference that in England, over the centuries, the nationalities (other than the Irish) were genuinely absorbed into the English nation. So, on the one hand – according to the concept – there was a Hungarian 'state nation' in the Carpathian Basin – which the nationalities basically rejected – and on the other hand the same existed within the Monarchy, which, apart from being treated with reservations by the Austrian side, could be challenged constitutionally on the grounds of lack of genuine sovereignty.

Considering that the concept of the Hungarian 'nation-state' could not be realized in the political reality of dualism, it did not place its validity on an adequate historical basis in relation to the current situation. Such was the case with the Golden Bull of 1222, the application of the symbolism of the Holy Crown within a modern framework, or the treatment of the medieval state framework and borders as all-decisive facts – and all this (partly) as a defence against the increasingly realistic aspirations of nationalities for self-government.

The difference, however, is that while Romanian nationalism goes back to antiquity for self-justification and is based on a (semi-) mythical past, in Hungary the historical tradition of the medieval kingdom was the reference point before the First World War. The return to the misty past became a dominant narrative only in the Horthy era – although the Hun consciousness first emerged and took shape during the dualism.

After 1920, both versions of Hungarian nationalism were in crisis; with the dissolution of the historical state framework, the concept of the 'state-nation' was no longer valid, and the 'cultural-national' borders did not include a significant part of the Hungarian-speaking population. In the 1920s and '30s, in the search for a new way forward, catalysed by the German and Italian examples, the idea of race not only appeared on the national ideological stage but also affected civil rights –

in parallel with this, ideologies centred on prehistory gained ground; Turanism virtually reached the level of the state.

Conclusion

The concept of nationalism has its roots in the late 18th century, and over the following 100 years two main forms of nationalism emerged in European countries. Romanian nationalism, after its emergence in the mid-19th century, was transformed by the early 20th century into a rather uncommon form that essentially based on the framework of the 'German-type' model, despite the realities of the country's ethnic distribution. Another specific feature of the Romanian nationalist tradition is that, unlike the nationalist conceptions of the West, and even more fundamentally of Central Europe the role of the peasantry as the core part of the nation was of substantial importance due to the result of the country's inorganic social development.

To sum up, in the early 20th century, both Romanian and Hungarian state nationalisms were, in practical terms, meant to justify territorial claims and to justify an existing situation – Transylvania being the main case – but it is also evident that these two historicised nationalisms were also a substitute for something else. In both cases, we are faced with incomplete national development, so the historical arguments are strong – and the more the gap was felt, the more social gaps widened or the 'national conscience' emerged, the more the process was catalysed; the more the historical elements emerged and the more the pool of potential 'answers' to crisis situations was narrowed down to emotional explanations.

The historical reality rather seems to be that, after the First World War, it would have been impossible to draw clear lines between *Kulturnations* virtually anywhere in the Central- and Eastern European region. Nowhere was a French-style homogeneous nation-state created, but in the absence of any other political alternative, there was nothing to contain the further escalation of idea and programme of nationalism.

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7. The Transylvanian School was a movement in the late 18th century for the political and social emancipation of Romanians in Transylvania. Its representatives put forward historical and philological arguments in support of the thesis that Transylvanian Romanians were the direct descendants of the Roman settlers of Dacia.

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9. Boyars (boeri) were the nobility of the Danubian Principalities of Moldavia and Wallachia. The boyars held much of the political power in the principalities and – until the Phanariote era – they elected the ruler of the principality.

10. Mica Unire – The unification of Wallachia and Moldavia on 24 January 1859. The state was officially called the United Principalities until the 1866 Constitution.

11. The Moți are a Romanian people living in the central Apuseni Mountains, mostly in northeastern Alba county and in the south of Bihor county – in the region known as the 'Land of the Moții' (Țara Moților).

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16. For an example, based on the data of the 1930 Romanian census the population of Cluj/Kolozsvár/Klausenburg was 47,3% Hungarian and 34,6% Romanian. In the case of Ora-dea/Nagyvárad/Großwardein it was 51,5% Hungarian and 27,1% Romanian, and in Braşov/Brassó/Kronstadt it was 39,1% Hungarian, 32,7% Romanian and 22,1% German. Source: *Recensământul general al populației României, 1930*. Editura Institutului Central de Statistică, Bucureşti, 1938. Online: <https://dspace.bcuccluj.ro/handle/123456789/176865> . Date of download: 20. 03. 2025.

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21. The Golden Bull (Aranybulla) was an edit issued by King Andrew II of Hungary who was forced by his nobility to accept the bull, which was one of the first examples of constitutional limits being placed on the powers of a European monarch – a document similar to the 1215 Magna Carta Libertatum of England.

22. Turanism is a pan-nationalist political movement based on pseudo-scientific claims about biological and linguistic links between different ethnic groups in Eurasia, and builds on the theory of the Ural-Altaic language family, which assumes that the Turkic, Mongol, Tunguz and Uralic peoples share common Inner- and Central Asian origins and are therefore bound together by close cultural, ethnic and linguistic ties. The movement emerged in the 19th century in opposition to pan-nationalist ideologies such as pan-Germanism, and was based on the ideas of pan-Slavism as well.